

Implementation of a Visible Light Communications testbed in FPGA

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Abstract—Dedicated software defined testbeds for communication systems performance evaluation presents many advantages over using standard laboratory equipment, providing high reconfigurability and custom features design. This paper presents an FPGA-based implementation for visible light communications (VLC) systems with multiband carrierless amplitude and phase (m-CAP) modulation. In this work, a Digilent Eclipse Z7 development board was used, along with DAC and ADC daughterboards. Concerning the hardware design, the blocks data generation, m-CAP modulation, carrier generation, receiver synchronism, and bit error rate (BER) analyzer were designed using the Xilinx System Generator tool. The implementation includes a ARM microprocessor for data acquisition and the testbed configuration, using UART communication with a MatLab script. The testbed was experimentally validating using the target VLC system, and the results show the VLC system performance in terms of BER and symbol constellations, acquired with the testbed.

Keywords—FPGA, communication systems testbed, VLC, Xilinx, Eclipse Z7

I. INTRODUCTION

In the context of the Internet of things (IoT) the developments in electronic communication technologies and the growing trend in devices' miniaturization are leading to a progressively increase of Internet connected devices. According to [1], most of the connections are machine-to-machine (M2M) communications, which means that they are autonomously performed without any human intervention. Some applications are already part of our lives, such as home automation, health monitoring (i.e. smartwatches), traffic lights control, logistic management, automatic billing, access control, sensing and monitoring systems and industry 4.0 [2]. Future communication networks are expected to accommodate dozens or even hundreds of devices per m^3 , also known as massive machine-type communications (mMTC), while requiring low-cost, low-power, and reduced environmental impact [3].

Although current M2M wireless technologies are radio-frequency (RF) based, alternative technologies have been proposed to overcome some of RF drawbacks in mMTC scenarios such as increased packet collisions and the need of licensing. Visible light communication (VLC) is a technology that uses light to establish a communication link and has several benefits when compared with RF, such as license-free, highly reusable spectrum within few meters and electromagnetic interference improved resilience. This technology has considerable improved during the last decade, including the development of system models for the channel and analog frontends, the use

of complex modulation schemes such as orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) and orthogonal frequency division multiple access (OFDMA). Multi-band carrierless amplitude and phase (mCAP) modulation for VLC have been proposed by several authors as an alternative modulation scheme, presenting improved spectral efficiency [4] and allowing the use of the independent bands to address multiple-user access (MA) scenarios. The MA feature is of utmost importance in mMTC scenarios, making VLC-based systems using mCAP modulation a strong candidate for future wireless networks.

Although mCAP have been experimentally verified for MA schemes [5], the IoT requirements in terms of the devices' power consumption and cost are not commonly addressed. A solution to fulfil such requirements may consider a simplification of the receiver (Rx) circuits, for instance by using analog Rx architectures, allowing their implementation with fewer active components. This paper presents a FPGA implementation of a testbed for a VLC-based IoT system using analog m-CAP receivers. The testbed should be able to simultaneously generate a data stream, perform m-CAP modulation (to be sent to the communication system), acquire the demodulated signal, and measure the bit error rate (BER). When compared to a typical experimental setup using laboratory measurement equipment, the advantage of having a software defined testbed is their flexibility and the possibility of their improvement, progressively allowing new functions implementation. Thus, the testbed presented in this paper may implement further features in the future or even some functions may be removed in the receiver side, as they become implemented in the Rx hardware and are no longer needed in the testbed.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: section II presents the system architecture and the requirement goals, section III shows the system implementation, the results will be shown in section IV, and lastly, section V finalizes the paper with the conclusions.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The system block diagram of the VLC testbed is shown in Fig. 1. The system can be perceived as 3 parts: (a) the MatLab user interface, (b) the implemented testbed, and (c) the VLC system to be tested. The goal of the proposed testbed is to provide the means to test a VLC system performance. The VLC system input is an analog m-CAP signal and the output are the analog data symbols, I and Q . At its output, the testbed should generate the m-CAP signal to be transmitted, as well as the synchronized carriers to the receiver side. For the used

Fig. 1: Testbed system block diagram comprising the MatLab user interface, the implemented testbed, and the VLC system to be tested.

VLC system, the m-CAP signal to be generated is defined as follows:

$$y(k) = \sqrt{2} \sum_{m=1}^M (s_I^m(k) * F_I^m(k) - s_Q^m(k) * F_Q^m(k)), \quad (1)$$

where k is the sample index, M is the total number of bands, s_I and s_Q are the data symbols, F_I^m and F_Q^m are the in-phase I , and quadrature Q , filters, respectively. The filters' coefficients are given by (2) and (3), where $p(k)$ is a pulse shaping filter and $\omega_c^m = 2\pi f_c^m$, f_c^m is the central frequency on the m^{th} band, and F_s is the sampling frequency.

$$F_I^m(k) = p(k) \cos\left(\frac{\omega_c^m}{F_s} k\right), \quad (2)$$

$$F_Q^m(k) = p(k) \sin\left(\frac{\omega_c^m}{F_s} k\right). \quad (3)$$

The central frequencies for each band are given as $f_c^m = B(2m - 1)/2$, where B is the bandwidth of each band. As opposed to typical m-CAP systems where Nyquist filters are used, $p(k)$ need to be a matched filter with the filters used in the Rx. Therefore, for the implemented hybrid m-CAP/QAM system Bessel filters will be used, as discussed in [6].

At the Rx side, the testbed should sample and synchronize the Rx symbols, and provide the results to the user, namely: (i) BER and (ii) symbol constellations. The user should be able to set some parameters of the system, such as the carrier offset, the Rx symbol offset, and the DC level offset at the Rx symbols. This is performed by a UART interface which is also used to acquire the BER and Rx symbols.

A. System requirements

In order to establish the system requirements, a brief analysis regarding the VLC system characteristics needs to be performed. The Table I summarizes the VLC system parameters. The system should be able to accommodate 100 bands with a bandwidth of 5 kHz, one for each Rx, with a total bandwidth of 1 MHz. The carrier generator for the Rx demodulation should be able to generate two square waves with 90° phase shift

TABLE I: VLC system parameters

Parameter	Value
Number of Rxs (bands)	100
Band bandwidth	10 kHz
Total bandwidth	1 MHz
Tx input amplitude range	± 1 V
Tx input impedance	50 Ω
Tx SNR	67 dB
Carrier waveform	square-wave
Carrier frequency	$n \cdot 5k Hz, n \in \mathbb{N}$
Carrier amplitude range	3.3 V
Rx output amplitude range	± 1 V
Rx output bandwidth	5 kHz
Rx SNR	56 dB

between them, for the I and Q demodulation. The frequency value can be any value multiple of 5 kHz, up to 1 MHz in order to demodulate different bands. Considering the VLC system parameters, the testbed hardware requirements can now be set. The Table II presents specifications for the testbed hardware.

TABLE II: Testbed hardware specifications

Parameter	Value
DSP performance	>160 GMACs
DSP resolution	>16-bit
DAC sampling frequency	>2 MSPS
DAC bandwidth	>1 MHz
DAC output range	$< \pm 1$ V
DAC resolution	>12 bit
ADC resolution	>10 bit
ADC input range	$< \pm 1$ V
UART baudrate	>115200 bps

The DSP performance is computed as $2NR \times n_{coeff}$, where $N = 100$ is the number of bands, $R = 2$ MSPS the sampling rate, and $n_{coeff} = 400$ the number of coefficients in each m-CAP filter. The DAC sampling frequency and bandwidth are selected according to the system bandwidth. The DAC and ADC resolutions are defined for the VLC system SNR, so that the quantization SNR is lower than the frontends SNR. A fast UART is required for the transmission of the constellation symbols with a fair resolution. Besides the requirements in Table II, the system should have a processing unit that allows the results reading and parameters configuration of the remaining system.

B. FPGA block diagram

The block diagram of the FPGA design architecture is shown in Fig. 2. Three main blocks need to be developed for this testbed: 1) *BER_analyser*, 2) *mCAP_Tx_Rx*, and 3) *sqr_carrier_gen*. The configuration and data acquisition of these three blocks are both performed by a general purpose input/output (GPIO) block, connected to the embedded microprocessor via AXI-lite interface. The microprocessor includes a UART interface that establishes the connection with the user, allowing the configuration and data acquisition in real-time.

The three mentioned main blocks are able to operate in standalone mode, performing the tasks of modulating and

Fig. 2: FPGA block diagram.

recovery the data symbols (the blocks inside *mCAP_Tx_Rx*), as well as the BER computation, which is continuously computed, and the carrier generation. The blocks can be configured as follows: 1) the *symbol delay* can be configured in the *BER_analyser*, allowing synchronism between the Tx and Rx data; 2) the *Rx symbol offset* can be adjusted to remove residual voltage offset at the ADC inputs, effectively centering the constellation points; 3) the *carrier delay* configuration allows phase alignment to compensate for the channel delay. Regarding the data acquisition, two measurements can be obtained via the GPIO block: 1) *Rx symbols*, comprising both *I* and *Q* symbol values at the optimal sample time instant, prior to the decision, allowing visualization of the constellation; 2) BER performance, namely the number of Rx symbols and the number of Rx erroneous symbols.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

This section describes the implementation details of the proposed testbed, in particular the tools and platform choice, hardware design details, and software design.

A. Tools and platform

Considering the hardware requirements mentioned in section II-A, a Digilent Eclipse Z7 development board was selected to implement the testbed. This development board has everything required for this project, in particular it features a Xilinx XC7Z020-1CLG484C FPGA that comprises DSP processing capabilities up to 240 GMACs, enough programmable logical slices for the remaining blocks, as well as an embedded 677 MHz dual-core Cortex-A9 processor with 1 GB DDR3 RAM, which includes a UART transceiver. The Eclipse Z7 board also features 2 SYZYGY interfaces, allowing the connection of two Digilent Zmod daughter-boards: one Zmod AWG and one Zmod Scope that implements the DAC and ADC, respectively. The selected Zmod boards fulfil the hardware requirements, in particular they have 14-bit of resolution, and the bandwidth is much higher than the required for both boards.

Regarding the software design, the main blocks are implemented with Xilinx System Generator 2019.1, and then integrated with the remaining hardware blocks using Xilinx

Vivado 2019.1. The System Generator is a Xilinx tool for fast design and validation of Xilinx hardware design, which uses MatLab Simulink environment so that the design can be validated under the Simulink and then exported as a Xilinx IP core to Vivado. The embedded processor programming is done with the Xilinx SDK 2019.1, using C programming language. In the user side, MatLab 2018b is used for interfacing with the UART, allowing the user to request data and/or perform the system configurations.

B. Hardware design

The Fig. 3 presents a high level view of the main blocks implementation in the System Generator. In the Fig. 3a both m-CAP modulator and demodulator are implemented, as well as the symbol optimal sample time synchronism mechanism. In the Tx, the multiplexer selects if the modulated signal are the data symbols or the pilot symbols for the synchronism mechanism. The pilot symbols consists in a known sequence that allows the recovery of the optimal sample time instant. The data is modulated by upsampling and filtering the data with FIR filters, which is implemented in the FPGA DSPs. The filter coefficients are generated in the MatLab environment and fed directly in the System Generator model. In the receiver side, the upsampled received symbols are sampled by an ADC and a DC offset adjustment is applied to correct some of the Rx hardware imperfections. The oversampled Rx samples are then time corrected and a single sample for each symbol is retrieved at the optimal sample time instant, reducing the sampling rate to the symbol rate. The final step is to decode the symbol via hard decoding. Regarding the optimal sampling time recovery, a dedicated block is implemented with a finite-state machine that finds the optimal sampling time of the upsampled Rx symbols and returns the symbol delay in terms of the number of delayed samples in relation to the Tx signal.

The BER analyzer block is shown in Fig. 3b. As said, the main tasks of this block is to generate the Tx data and compare it with the Rx data. The data is generated with a pseudo-random generator, implemented with a linear feedback shift register, which generates '0's and '1's with equal probability. The data is asynchronously generated with relatively high rate and it is stored in a FIFO to be later read by the modulator. Two counters are implemented to count the number of Rx symbols, N_{sym} , and Rx erroneous symbols, N_{err} . The latest counter is only activated when the Rx symbol is different from the Tx symbol, delayed by a multiple of the symbol period, which is totally configurable.

Lastly, the square wave carrier generator, Fig.3c, produces the *I* and *Q* waveforms to be used in the Rx. By using a counter and a logical comparator, the input clock frequency is divided into the desired frequency and applies a programmable time shift for carrier synchronization. From this signal, a delay is applied to generate the quadrature carrier.

These three blocks were designed and validated in the Xilinx System Generator, and then exported to individual Xilinx IP cores to be added in Vivado. The input and output of the *mCAP_Tx_Rx* were connected to the ADC and DAC IP cores, respectively, and the carriers were connected directly to the FPGA output pins. The configuration signals were connected to a GPIO IP core, which in turns is connected to the processor.

Fig. 3: System Generator design: (a) m-CAP modulator/demodulator + symbol synchronization, (b) BER analyzer, (c) square wave carriers generator.

C. Software design

The embedded processor programming was performed in Xilinx SDK, using C programming language. The program implements the following tasks, all accessible via UART:

- read the Rx constellation points in real-time

- read the BER statistics: number of the total Rx symbols and the erroneous Rx symbols
- configure the symbol delay
- configure carrier delay
- configure DC offset of Rx symbols, individually for I and Q

The user interface is performed with MatLab. A MatLab script was written, allowing the user to insert commands which performs the testbed configuration and retrieves the testbed data. Furthermore, two scripts were written in order to automatically find the most adequate symbol delay and DC offset. The script to find the symbol delay iteratively configures the symbol delay value until it finds no changes in the BER, whereas the script to compensate for the Rx symbols DC offset looks into the average value of the I and Q components and iteratively adjusts the DC offset.

IV. RESULTS

This section presents the implemented testbed validation as well as the results obtained in conjunction with the VLC system. The implementation considers only one modulated band, the second band of the system, with central frequency of 15 kHz.

The resources utilization of the implemented design is shown in Table III. Two main conclusions can be derived from the table: 1) the chosen FPGA has enough resources to implement the proposed testbed; 2) Considering that only one band is implemented, the DSPs utilization is relatively high. However, since the sampling frequency in the DSPs is 2 MHz and the DSPs clock is 100 MHz, the DSPs can be multiplexed for the remaining bands.

The FPGA was programmed and all the connections were made to the VLC system. The first step is to synchronize the carrier wave with the Rx signal, which was performed with an oscilloscope and adjusting the carrier phase with the UART interface. Next, the DC offset is automatically compensated with the MatLab script, as well as the symbol delay adjustment is computed. These tasks are performed in a very close range between the Tx and the Rx in order to guarantee a maximal signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), to achieve the best possible adjustment.

TABLE III: FPGA resource utilization of the implemented design

Resource	Utilization (%)	Total
Slice LUTs	13.8%	53200
Slice registers	7.2%	106400
F7 Muxes	7.7%	26600
F8 Muxes	21.7%	13300
Slice	5.8%	53200
LUT as Logic	6.2%	53200
LUT as Memory	23.3%	17400
Block RAM Tile	56.8%	140
DSPs	36.1%	220

Fig. 4: Rx constellations for d of 1.4, 1.7, 2.0 and 2.3 m.

Fig. 5: BER vs. the distance between Tx and Rx.

The Rx constellation is shown in Fig. 4, for different distances d between Tx and Rx, in a line-of-sight configuration, which also shows the reference constellation. For all the distances, a total of 5000 symbols were acquired, and the constellation was later normalized to 1 W. As expected, the constellation dispersion increases with the d . It can also be seen in the figure that the DC offset compensation task, as well as the carrier phase adjustment was successfully achieved since the constellation is centered and presents no rotation, respectively.

After the symbol synchronization procedure in MatLab, the BER was obtained by using the data returned from the *BER_analyzer* block, at different distances between Tx and Rx, computed as:

$$BER \approx \frac{SER}{2} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{N_{err}}{N_{sym}} \quad (4)$$

where SER is the symbol error rate. Since the constellations are mapped using a Grey code, we can assume that the BER is approximately half of the SER value. The Fig. 5 presents the computed BER in respect to the Tx and Rx distance. For each distance, N_{sym} value was guaranteed to be at least ten times higher than N_{err} , to ensure statistical significance of the measured BER value. Thus, both values were consecutively read until two conditions were met: $N_{err} \geq 100$ and $N_{sym} \geq 10N_{err}$. As expected, the BER value degrades with the increasing distance.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed a testbed design, implementation and validation for m-CAP VLC systems. Building dedicated

testbeds offers several advantages over the usual experimental setups in communications laboratories since they are highly reconfigurable, providing custom data to the user. Furthermore, a dedicated testbed can implement specific functions and modulations that are usually not present in commercial systems. In this particular case, m-CAP modulation with a custom filter is easily implemented by changing the coefficients of the FIR filter, also allowing the usage of different coefficients, if needed. The implementation of this testbed also shows the importance of having a dedicated microprocessor, allowing the construction of a custom user interface, implementing simple functions for system configuration and data retrieve.

The design and validation of the testbed was simplified by the usage of the System Generator environment, and a relatively complex system was reduced to few main System Generator blocks, such as FIR Compilers for configuring the DSPs, Mcode for the finite state machine of the symbol synchronism, addressable shift registers for the various reconfigurable delay lines, totally configured in the Simulink environment. The testbed was successfully implemented in the FPGA, presenting a general low resource utilization, which allows future design updates to include new features, such as more modulated bands, dynamic FIR filter coefficient reconfiguration for other pulse shaping filter, eye diagrams, computation of error vector magnitude, connection to a Gigabit Ethernet port for real data transmission, among others. Regarding the user perspective, the experiments proved that is easy to reconfigure and read data with the implemented testbed, only requiring the input of few characters in the MatLab command window.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work is funded by FCT/MCTES through national funds and when applicable co-funded EU funds under the project UIDB/50008/2020-UIDP/50008/2020.

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